

SUSTAINABILITY MECHANISM FOR POSH HOTELIER EMPLOYEES BY ASSESSING OF THEIR TURNOVER INTENTION AND ISSUES

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ABSTRACT

Researchers in hospitality management have evinced keen interest in the past decades to study the high employee turnover which is an important issue for many hoteliers not only in management but also in sustainable development of hotels in India. In spite of the retention techniques adopted by the hoteliers, the employee turnover rate remains high. It is significant to note that employee morale is not only affected by high turnover rates but it also leads to loss of effective employees. In a highly competitive situation, the hotel industry should rely on an effective as well as sustainable management of employees and must reduce the turnover rates. There is a need to understand the service climate and associated aspects to evaluate the underlying mechanism in the hotel industry with respect to employee turnover. The present study is attained to identify the turnover intension and its related issues to formulate an approach for sustainable mechanism for employee retention. The two categories of turnover intensions are voluntary and involuntary turnover intension. The decision by employee themselves to leave the organization is termed as voluntary turnover intention. The departure of an employee which will be directed by the employer is involuntary turnover intension. A case study was carried out in Ramada Hotel, a star category of luxury hotel located in Chennai. The case study deals with four core operational departments. A self-administered questionnaire was distributed to 150 employees of the luxury hotel. After a thorough review of the returned questionnaire, 140 were obtained appropriately and complete were used for the analysis. We have used some statistical techniques for the analysis of the data collected. The results of this study indicated that the demographic factors such as gender, age, education, marital status as well as the factors such as wage, tenure, working department, and position are the determinations of turnover intentions.

(Keywords: Hospitality Industry, Happiness, Turn Over Intention & Job Satisfaction)

1. Introduction

The hospitality industry in India is one of the largest one. It covers many segments and employment sectors. It is observed that this industry faces many challenges and the workforce is a unique one being a major part that affects sustainable development. The industry often relies on part time and seasonal workers. In recent years research relating to turnover in hospitality industry has attracted many researches. In this study an attempt is made to analyse the turnover related aspects in Chennai, Tamilnadu.

1.1 Definitions of Employee Turnover and Turnover Intentions

Employee Turnover is also referred as labor turnover and widely interchangeably used. Price (1977) has defined employee turnover as “The number of organizational members leaving during a period divided by the average number of people in the organization during the period”. Walker (1992) has stated that the ratio of number of employees leaving organization in a particular tie period to the number of employees still working in the organization is defined as employee turnover.

Home and Griffeth (1995) [figure 1.1] classified turnover into voluntary and involuntary turnover. Involuntary turnover is often employer initiated and the employees has no say.

Figure 1.1.1 Employee Turnover

Voluntary turnover is classified into two categories i.e., functional and dysfunctional. A voluntary exit can be considered functional if the existing employee was a non-performance.

Katsikeuetal; (2015) has stated that the reduction in total number of employees who plan to leave their job is defined as employee turnover. Lambert etal; (2013) has defined that when an employee thinks or plan to exit an organization it is turnover intention.

1.2: Objectives of the study.

- a. To study in detail the age structure, educational qualification, length of service in hotel industry, and categories of position.
- b. To construct a discriminant model for identifying the factors which discriminates between the male and female employees of the sampled data in respect of the turnover intentions.

The paper is structured as noted below. In section 2, we have presented an updated review of literature on employee turnover and employee turnover intention. Section 3 deals with the details relating to case-study attempted. A detailed account of discriminant analysis of the sampled data is presented in section 4. Results and conclusions based on the case study is given in section 5.

2. Literature Survey on Employee Turnover and Employee Turnover Intention –

Dipietro and Candy (2007) analyzed that employee turnover based on Commitment and Necessary Effect (CANE) model of Motivation in the hospitality industry. They have used regression analysis and found that motivation component of CANE model is statistically

significant one when turnover analysis is attempted.

Jen-Te Yang, Chin-Sheng and Yi-Jui Fu (2012) have identified the motivating factors behind workers decisions to leave an organization and examined the specific retention approaches to decrease turnover rates in Taiwanese Hotel Industry.

Awang and Osama (2013) have noted that the turnover intention is the behavioral attitude of an employee who is desiring to withdraw from an organization and is an actual predictor of the actual turnover. They have emphasized the need for setting additional reliable information on the factors influencing turnover intention. Byrant and Allen (2013) presented a wide variety of effective strategies to support in managing the turnover rate.

Faldetta et al., (2013) and Al Batta and Sam (2013) have stressed the need for the study of employee turnover in hotel industry and the factors related to the employee turnover in the hotel industry. They have pointed out the suggestions for positive and social change in the hotel industry. Kumar and Chahal (2013) have stated that high employee turnover rates of hotel industry are amongst the highest challenges that human resource management face.

Pearlman and Schaffer (2013) have stated that high employee turnover rates of hotel industry are amongst the highest challenges that human resource management face. Guilding et al., (2014) studied in detail the cost aspects associated with turnover rates. Asad Mohsin et al., (2015) in their study assessed the connection between the intention to leave job and its antecedents with respect to the staffs of luxury hotels in India, is linear or quadratic, they found that earnings job security, and loyalty are found to be direct. Organizational enthusiasm and interesting job established a quadratic connection.

Harley (2015) studied the importance of prioritizing employee's well-being in the work place to certain employee turnover and stated that turnover could directly affect consumer satisfaction. Narayanan (2016) examined the talent management and employee retention. Dilbag Singh and Ananddeep (2017) studied the impact of turnover in hotel industry based on related hotels in Delhi.

Hee Jung Kang et al., (2018) developed a conceptual model of service eliminate the hospitality industry. They tested the relationship between model of service eliminate the hospitality industry. They have demonstrated the significance of service eliminate in considering the turnover intention of hotel management.

3. A case study for understanding turnover intentions.

3.1: Case study and its sampling design.

The case study has been carried out based on the data collected through a questionnaire. The format of the questionnaire is given in the appendix. Totally 181 employees have responded for the case-study. A Detailed questionnaire has been framed incorporating the objectives of the study.

It is important to note that scaling technique has been used in respect of the correlation of data based on Part-2, Part-3 and Part-4 aspects noted above. Part-2 is based on 7- point scale, Part-3 and Part-4 is based on the 5- point scale. The data has been collected through the online questionnaire form. The data was thoroughly checked for its consistency. Reliability of the data has also been investigated.

3.2 Data Structure and the Results

The study consists of data obtained from 181 respondents and the details of the case study in respect of the construction of discriminant model is presented in the subsequent sections.

3.2.1 Demographic profile of employees

The age distribution of the respondents is presented in the following Table 3.2.1 (a). The data indicates that majority of the employees fall in the 35-50 age category and only few constitutes the age category 50-60.

Table 3.2.1 (a): Age Distribution of Employees			
Age	Male	Female	Total
15-35	55 (50*)	19 (26.8*)	74 (40.9*)
35-50	50 (45.5*)	40 (56.3*)	90 (49.7*)
50-60	5 (4.5*)	12 (16.9*)	17 (9.4*)
Total	110	71	181
* Represents percentage			

The educational status of the respondents is given in Table 3.2.1 (b). Around 90% of the respondents have qualified themselves either diploma or graduation.

Table 3.2.1 (b): Educational Status of Employees			
Educational Qualification	Male	Female	Total
Graduate	46 (41.8*)	44 (62*)	90 (49.7*)
Diploma	52 (47.3*)	22 (31*)	74 (40.9*)
Below Matriculation	7 (6.4*)	5 (7*)	12 (6.6*)
Other Categories	5 (4.5*)	0	5 (2.8*)
Total	110	71	181
* Represents percentage			

The years of service in hotel industry is given in Table 3.2.1 (c). Around one fourth of the employees have years of service 1-5 years, nearly 60% of employees have put in more than 5 years but within 15 years. Only 9% of employees have more than 15 years of service.

Table 3.2.1 (c): Years of Service in Hotel Industry			
Year/s of Service	Male	Female	Total
Less than one year	4 (3.6*)	5 (7*)	9 (5*)
1-5 year	38 (34.5*)	7 (9.9*)	45 (24.9*)
5-10 year	33 (30*)	21 (29.6*)	54 (29.8*)
10-15 year	26 (23.6*)	30 (42.3*)	56 (30.9*)
More than 15 years	9 (8.2*)	8 (11.3*)	17 (9.4*)

Total	110	71	181
* Represents percentage			

3.2.2 Profile relating to position, working department & category of shift:

The categories of position of employees are presented in Table 3.2.2 (a). Only 11% of employees are in executive category. It is interesting to note that 38% of female employees are working as managers and around 50% of employees are occupied by the categories namely supervisor and other related positions.

Position	Male	Female	Total
Executive	2 (1.8*)	18 (25.4*)	20 (11*)
Manager	44 (40*)	27 (38*)	71 (39.2*)
Superior	34 (30.9*)	16 (22.5*)	50 (27.6*)
Other	30 (27.3*)	10 (14.1*)	40 (22.1*)
Total	110	71	181
* Represents percentage			

The working department details are presented in Table 3.2.2 (b). It is to be noted that 18% of employees are working in front desk/guest service section and this is a vital section in hotel industries. Only around 7% of employees are working as department heads and we find that there is wide variation with respect to the number of employees working in different categories of department and this is a realistic phenomenon.

Working Department	Male	Female	Total
Front desk/guest service	17 (15.5*)	16 (22.5*)	33 (18.2*)
F&B	17 (15.5*)	4 (5.6*)	21 (11.6*)
Marketing	11 (10*)	4 (5.6*)	15 (8.3*)
Finance	8 (7.3*)	13 (18.3*)	21 (11.6*)
Operation	10 (9.1*)	10 (14.1*)	20 (11*)
Housekeeping	8 (7.3*)	7 (9.9*)	15 (8.3*)
Others (Please specify)	14 (12.7*)	4 (5.6*)	18 (9.9*)
HR	9 (8.2*)	4 (5.6*)	13 (7.2*)
Purchase	8 (7.3*)	5 (7*)	13 (7.2*)
Dept. Head	8 (7.3*)	4 (5.6*)	12 (6.6*)
Total	110	71	181
* Represents percentage			

The category of shift of employees is presented in Table 3.2.2 (c). Around 60% of the employees are working in general shift while the number of females working in general shift is more in number compared to men. Only 2% of the male employees prefer to work in overnight shifts and only a few female employees prefer to work at different types of shifts.

Shift	Male	Female	Total
Grave yard (overnight)	3 (2.7*)	0	3 (1.7*)
Swing	20 (18.2*)	8 (11.3*)	28 (15.5*)
Work after different types of shifts	36 (32.7*)	6 (8.5*)	42 (23.2*)
General	51 (46.4*)	57 (80.3*)	108 (59.7*)
Total	110	71	181
* Represents percentage			

4. Discriminant Analysis Model

The results of the DA will be more reliable when the sample size is greater than 30 for each independent variable in the analysis.

The author of this research paper for the first-time attempted discriminant analysis for the employees in respect of hotel industry in Chennai. For constructing discriminant made we have used sampled data from the data collected. The study consists of 40 male and 40 female employees.

X1 = Age

X2 = Years of Service

X3 = Happiness Index (HI).

X4 = Job Satisfaction Index (JSI).

X5 = Turnover Intention Index (TOI).

We observe the following based on the results given in the above analysis.

- I. The average age and average years of service of female employees is greater than male employees.
- II. The happiness index, JSI and TOI is comparatively more in the case of male employees than female employees.

It is important to note that there exist significant differences between male and female employees in respect of age, year of service, happiness, job satisfaction for which the p values are less than 0.05, which is the assumed level of significance. It is noticed from the values that there is no significant difference, in the mean in respect of turnover intention as the p value is >0.05.

The discriminant function clearly indicates that the predictor variable viz. The above analysis shows that Happiness Index is the most important predictor variable in this research, with a correlation coefficient of 0.815. It's worth noting that the relative relevance of the variables has changed since the standardized discriminant function was applied. The inter correlation between the predictor variables causes a shift in the relative relevance of the variables when employing a structural matrix as opposed to a standardized coefficient.

5. Results and Conclusion:

- (1) The detailed analysis has shown that there exist significant differences between the male and female employees means for predictor variables viz; age, years of service, happiness and job satisfaction indices.
- (2) There does not exist significant differences between the male and female employees in the means for the predictor analysis in Turn Over Index (TOI).
- (3) The statistical test of significance for wilk's lambda reveals that the discriminant function is significant.
- (4) The results of structure matrix specify that Happiness Index (HI) is the most important predictor variable and this plays an important role in employee retention which in turn supports in sustainable development of the hotel.
- (5) The classification matrix shows that 85% of the developed cases are correctly classified and this demonstrates that the discriminant model developed can be considered as a valid one.
- (6) The findings of the study may aid hotel management in developing procedures to reduce staff turnover intentions and lead to a development in the industry on sustainability aspects.

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